

THERMAL CYCLING DAMAGE OF SiC WHISKER/2124 ALUMINUM

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Summary

Thermal cycling tests were conducted on 15% volume fraction of SiC whisker/2124 aluminum composites by using cold (room temperature) and hot ($T_{\max} = 673$ and 773K) fluidized baths, followed by mechanical tests with the aim of studying the effect of thermal cycling on the residual mechanical properties. It was found that the thermal cycling at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$ degraded the composite more severely than at 773K .

Introduction

For a number of years, the interest in the effects of thermal cycling on the microstructure and mechanical properties of metal-matrix composites has grown. General interest has also been growing in silicon carbide reinforced aluminum (SiC/Al) since the advent of "rice hull technology" (1-9). And while considerable effort has been focused on the study of the effects of thermal cycling on other composite systems such as boron/aluminum (10-12), tungsten/copper (13-15), and others (16,17), whisker reinforced composites in general have not received the same degree of attention. The objective of this study is to present some basic information on the effects of thermal cycling on a SiC/Al composite as the first step within a larger study.

Thermal cycling damage mechanisms can be categorized as: plastic deformation of the matrix, reinforcement damage or failure, weakening of the fiber/matrix interface, and metallurgical instability of the constituent phases (11,18). Plastic deformation of the matrix can manifest itself as macroscopic changes in sample dimensions (13,14,18), and of course a higher dislocation density in the matrix. These dislocations may "pile up" against the fibers possibly resulting in early fiber failure (18), and thus be related to the second mechanism. Fiber damage might also be attributable to mechanical fatigue associated with a large number of thermal cycling. Degradation of the fiber/matrix interface can take the form of void initiation as was the case for a tungsten/copper composite (13), and as cracking or embrittlement of the reaction layer as in the case of boron/aluminum composites (12,16), or simply debonding of the fibers (11). Metallurgical instability can result in the degradation of the fiber/matrix interface by the diffusion of oxygen (16) or an alloying element (12) to the interface. The leaching of an alloying element can also result in the weakening of the matrix.

The unfortunate result of the action of the mechanisms discussed above is the degradation of the material properties. Some composites such as boron/aluminum may experience severe losses of strength but no change in modulus (10,12), while other such as FP/Mg lose both strength and modulus (17). Similarly, the fracture mechanisms may change as in the cases of tungsten/copper (13) and boron/aluminum (12), which experienced increases in fiber pullout as a consequence of thermal cycling, or the mode of failure may remain unchanged as for SiC/titanium (16).

Experiment

The objective of this paper is to analyze the effects of thermal cycling on the tensile properties of a whisker reinforced metal-matrix composite. Samples of the composite were thermally cycled under various conditions and mechanically tested. Microscopic examinations of the as-cycled composite were made to find clues to failure mechanisms and plastic flow in the matrix. Microscopic examinations of the fracture surfaces were performed to determine the basic failure mechanism and monitor any changes in fracture morphology.

The material studied in this program was 2124-T6 aluminum reinforced with 15% volume fraction of silicon carbide whiskers (SiC) and was provided by Arco Silag. It was fabricated by hot pressing a mixture of aluminum powder and SiC whiskers, followed by extrusion, hot rolling, and heat treatment. The composite was supplied in the form of 6.35mm thick plate.

Rectangular samples 87mm x 40mm were cut from the stock plate, and the edges were machined flat. The major axis of each sample was made to

coincide with the predominant whisker orientation. Before and after thermal cycling, the dimensions of each sample were accurately measured to monitor dimensional changes. After cycling, the samples were cut into strips which were then machined into round tensile specimens following ASTM E-8-81 (19). Thermally cycling a plate instead of premachined specimens has the advantages of simplifying the transient heat conduction and thermal stress problems by simplifying the sample geometry. Experimentally, it also simplifies the sample holder design and handling procedures. Using a round tensile specimen design has the advantages of removing surface defects, and avoiding dimensional changes in the specimen during thermal cycling which might introduce unwanted geometric effects on the test results. The tensile tests were performed using an Instron static testing machine at a strain rate of .02mm/mm-min. Four replicates were tested from each sample, one of which was strain gauged to provide yield stress and longitudinal modulus data. Fracture surfaces were examined using a Phillips EM501 scanning electron microscope (SEM). A stub containing the fracture surface was cut from one specimen from each sample and was examined unetched.

Some of the leftover material from each as-cycled sample was used to make foils to be examined with a Phillips EM400 transmission electron microscope (TEM). Discs were prepared by wafering and then core drilling small blocks of the samples. The discs were thinned by a two-stage electrochemical process. Initial thinning was achieved by using a vertical jetting apparatus at about 30V and room temperature. Final thinning to perforation was done in a beaker at about 10V and 246K. The solution for both processes was 1/3 nitric acid and 2/3 methanol.

Five samples were tested in this program: one was as supplied by the manufacturer, and four were thermally cycled. For all of the runs, the lower temperature was set at 283K. Pairs of runs were performed at upper temperatures of 673K and 773K, for 100 and 1000 cycles each. The duration of each cycle was approximately 260 seconds with a dwell in each bed of 125 seconds per cycle (see Figure 1). The hot and cold temperature sources were two "home-made" fluidized alumina sand baths. A variac-controlled tube furnace was used for the hot bath, and a water chiller was used to provide a cold source for the 283K bath. Pneumatic pistons were used to cycle the samples between the baths. A schematic of the apparatus is given in Figure 2.

Experimental Results

Dimensional Stability

In two of the thermal cycling runs, significant changes in sample dimensions were observed. The changes after 1000 cycles are shown in Figure 3. Very small changes in the dimensions were observed after 100 cycles so those data are omitted for clarity.

For all of the samples, the magnitudes of the thickness changes were greater than for the other dimensions. The thickness also shrank while the in-plane dimensions (length and width) expanded. These effects seem to be related to the degree of whisker orientation along these directions. The whiskers are very well aligned in-plane through the thickness so that virtually all of the fibers are perpendicular to the thickness axis. The in-plane orientation, however, is not so uniform: a much larger percentage of the whiskers are off-axis to a significant degree. It seems then that the composite tends to plastically expand parallel to the fibers and shrink in the plane transverse to the fibers, possibly due to Poisson effects. This will be discussed more in details later.

Figure 1 - Time versus temperature trace of a sample cycled between 283K and 773K fluidized sand baths.

Figure 2 - Schematic of thermal cycling apparatus. The cold bath (on the right) is cooled by chilled water flowing through a copper coil. The hot bath (on the left) is heated by a variac-powered tube furnace.

Figure 3 - Changes in sample dimensions after 1000 thermal cycles. Note the in-plane expansion (of the length and width) versus the out-of-plane shrinkage of the thickness.

Figure 4 - TEM micrograph of as-fabricated composite. The dark regions are the SiC whiskers.

Figure 5 - TEM micrograph of a sample cycled 1000 times with $T_{max}=673K$. Note the higher dislocation density than for the as-fabricated sample, and the dislocation pileups along the grain boundaries.

Figure 6 - TEM micrograph showing the intersection of a grain boundary and dislocations with the end of a SiC whisker.

TEM Observations

TEM examinations of the as-fabricated (Figure 4) and as-cycled (Figure 5) composites were performed to identify thermal cycling damage mechanisms. A comparison between uncycled (Figure 4) and 1000 cycled at 673K (Figure 5) indicates that thermal cycling tends to increase dislocation density. The TEM pictures may not reveal the true dislocation morphology, since the electrochemical jetting process seemingly etched only the matrix metal which may have contained a great number of dislocations. Thus, we failed to observe as high dislocation densities as other authors (1,2). However, we have confirmed that dislocations were generated around fiber-ends (see Figure 6), which can be considered to be caused by the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficient between the matrix and fiber (2).

SEM Observations

Representative SEM pictures were taken of the fracture surfaces of the failed tensile specimens to characterize the mode of failure. Generally, all of the samples failed by dimple rupture, and no significant differences were found between the fractures of uncycled (Figure 7) or 1000 cycled specimens (Figure 8 for $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$ and Figure 9 for $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$). Most of the voids were large and were nucleated at the whiskers. The figures show the hexagonal cross-sections of the whiskers at the base of the voids, and a few pulled-out fibers. A few number of small voids were apparently nucleated at fine SiC particles. Fiber pullout was rarely found in any of the specimens in contrast to SiC fibers in 1100 and 6000 series aluminum matrices (9). However, it can be noted in Figures 7, 8, and 9 that the fractured surface of the cycled at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$ looks more flat than the uncycled and cycled at $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$. This may correspond to the fact that the cycled specimen at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$ was degraded more severely as evidenced from Figures 3, 11, and 12.

Tensile Test Results

Significant reduction in the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and yield strength resulted from thermal cycling. Figure 10 shows the stress-strain data for the as-fabricated composite and the two samples subjected to 1000 cycles. Little difference was observed between samples subjected to 100 or 1000 cycles, except in UTS of the samples cycled at 673K.

The as-supplied composite had a UTS of 637MPa, a yield strength of 410MPa, a longitudinal modulus of 97.2GPa, and a necking failure strain of 13%. The modulus was unaffected by thermal cycling, and the necking failure strain was slightly increased only for the sample cycled 1000 times at 673K.

The effect of thermal cycling on the UTS of the composite is shown in Figure 11. Thermal cycling at a maximum temperature of 673K caused a 23% reduction in UTS after 100 cycles and a 30% reduction after 1000 cycles. Cycling at 773K resulted in only a 7% reduction in UTS after 100 cycles and an 8% reduction after 1000 cycles. The maximum total range of scatter in the UTS values was less than 2%, so only the averages are shown in the figure.

The effects of thermal cycling on the yield strength are shown in Figure 12. Even larger reductions were found than for UTS. Cycling to 673K produced a 55% drop in yield strength after 100 cycles and a 57% drop after 1000 cycles. Cycling to 773K produced a drop of 36% after 100 cycles and 38% after 1000 cycles.

Figure 7 - SEM fractograph of the as-fabricated composite failed in tension. Two pulled-out whiskers can be seen in the center of the picture, and whisker ends can be seen at the bases of many of the dimples.

Figure 8 - SEM fractograph of a composite sample cycled 1000 times with $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$.

Figure 9 - SEM fractograph of a composite sample cycled 1000 times with $T_{max} = 773K$.

Figure 10 - Longitudinal stress-strain plots for uncycled, and cycled composite samples. The failure points exceeded the elongation limits of the strain gages and are therefore not shown.

Figure 11 - UTS versus T_{max} . Note the greater dependency of UTS on T_{max} rather than on the number of thermal cycles.

Figure 12 - Yield strength versus T_{max} .

Much higher reductions in yield strength rather than UTS were observed, and no significant dependence on the number of cycles. While the reduction in UTS was less, there was some dependence on the number of cycles for the samples cycled to 673K.

Discussions

Change in a Sample Plate

The principal thermal cycling damage mechanism identified in this study is the plastic flow of the matrix as evidenced by significant changes in sample dimensions. However, the change in sample dimensions is not isotropic, the length and width of the composite plate expanded, whereas its thickness shrank as seen from Figure 3. The discrepancy between the changes in length, width and thickness can be explained as follows:

At 15% volume fraction of SiC whisker, whiskers are not completely aligned along the extrusion direction along which the length of samples are measured, but the majority of whiskers are misoriented with orientation angle θ with respect to the length direction. The range of θ is from $-\alpha$ to α where $|\alpha| \leq 90^\circ$, and the dependence of the fiber density on θ , $\rho(\theta)$ is considered to be symmetric with respect to $\theta = 0$ as shown in Figure 13. This gives rise to macroscopically orthotropic properties of a sample plate. Plastic strain in the matrix is caused by mainly $\Delta T \Delta \alpha$ where ΔT is the differential temperature, $|T_{\max} - T_{\min}|$ and $\Delta \alpha$ are defined by $|\alpha_f - \alpha_m|$ with α_f and α_m being the thermal expansion coefficient to the fiber along the fiber axis and matrix, respectively. For $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$ and $T_{\min} = 283\text{K}$, $\Delta T \Delta \alpha \approx 7.2 \times 10^{-3}$ which far exceeds the yield strain ϵ_y of the aluminum matrix at room temperature ($\epsilon_y \approx 1 \times 10^{-3}$). Thus, the matrix becomes yielded during thermal cycling. For each cycle, the stress-strain curve of the matrix would exhibit a histeris loop, leaving a permanent plastic strain $\Delta \epsilon_p$ in the matrix. This mechanism would give rise to the maximum permanent plastic strain in the matrix along the fiber axis, or in a macroscopic sense along the length direction. If no voids are generated in the composite during thermal cycling, then the expansion of a sample plate along the length and width directions should cause the shrinkage of the plate along the thickness direction since the matrix can be considered almost incompressible when the major portion of the matrix deforms plastically.

A direct application of the above reasoning to the results of the dimensional change at $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$ (see Figure 3) would make us puzzled. For the dimensional change in a sample plate is smaller at $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$ than at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$. However, this can be explained as follows. Creep of the matrix becomes more enhanced at higher temperature, and for $\Delta T > 0$ (path A to B in Figure 1), the matrix is subjected to compressive stress along the fiber axis (19,20), resulting in compressive creep strain in the matrix, while for $\Delta T < 0$ (path CD in Figure 1), the creep behavior of the matrix is reversed. Thus, the net permanent strain after thermal cycling would not be large. On the other hand, at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$ the deformation of the matrix is a mixed mode, elastic, time-dependent plastic and creep (time-dependent) deformation, and the role of the first two modes would be still substantial compared with creep mode. The plastic strains caused by both the heating process (path AB in Figure 1) and the cooling process (CD) are additive, resulting in the larger amount at the end of thermal cycling.

Figure 13 - Fiber density versus orientation angle. This distribution will affect the dimensional changes caused by thermal cycling, as well as the mechanical properties of the plate.

Yield Stress

The yield stress (σ_y) of thermally cycled SiC/Al composite is reduced from that of uncycled one as seen from Figure 12. However, σ_y at $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$ is smaller than that at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$. The reason for this is as follows. Recrystallization of aluminum alloy starts at about 623K and the higher the temperature (above 623K) and the longer the exposure time, the more enhancement of recrystallization. Though the exposure time for each thermal cycle is small, about 100 seconds, the repeated exposure (by thermal cycling) would cause recrystallization in SiC/Al composites. This is more enhanced at $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$. Hence, the thermally cycled SiC/Al composite specimen at $T_{\max} = 773\text{K}$ would have σ_y closer to the yield stress of uncycled specimen than that at $T_{\max} = 673\text{K}$.

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